

8-Methoxy-2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde Thiosemicarbazone as an Analytical Reagent for Cobalt(II) and Copper(II)

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Manuscript received 2 November 1993, revised 21 February 1994, accepted 18 May 1994

Thiosemicarbazones are used for the spectrophotometric determination of ions¹. The present work concerns the spectrophotometric determination of Co^{II} and Cu^{II} by 8-methoxy-2-chloroquinoline 3-carbaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (8-MeO-chloro-QAT).

Results and Discussion

8-MeO-2-chloro-QAT is soluble in DMF, water, ethanol and acetone, and insoluble in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and cyclohexanone. A 1.83×10^{-3} M solution of the reagent is stable for a week in 3 : 2 (v/v) water-DMF mixture. The Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are stable for 48 and 24 h respectively. The reagent in DMF-water showed maximum absorption at 360 nm. Dissociation constants of the complexes were determined by Job's and mole-ratio methods. The physical characteristic of the complexes are presented in Table 1.

for colour development. Co^{II}/Ni^{II} solution (1 mg/ml) was treated with 1.83×10^{-3} M 8-MeO-2-chloro-QAT and buffer solution (1 ml) to develop the complex. It was then diluted with water-DMF to 10 ml. The absorbance was measured at 350-650 nm against the reagent blank. Analytical parameters are presented in Table 1.

Effect of diverse ions : For the determination of Co (2 ppm) the tolerance limit (ppm) for different ions are as follows : Ga^{III} (80), Mo^{VI} (90), Ca^{II} (90), Sc (1000), oxalate (1000), thiourea (1000), phosphate (1000) and F (1000); Cu^{II}, Mn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Fe^{II} and citrate did not interfere. For Cu, the tolerance limit for various ions are as follows : Ca^{II} (100), Mn^{II} (5), Co^{II} (15), As^{III} (10), Pb^{II} (5), Sn^{II} (200), Bi^{III} (15), Ni^{II} (5), Fe^{II} (2), Cr^{VI} (5), Mg^{II} (20), U^{VI} (10), V^V (15), Ce^{IV} (50), W^{VI} (200), Ti^{IV} (20), Mo^{VI} (15), EDTA (30), acetate (100), chloride (100), citrate (10), phosphate (50) and oxalate (30); Zn^{II}, titrate and fluoride did not interfere.

The applicability of the method was tested by satisfactory analysis of the synthetic samples containing cobalt. The proposed method is simple and rapid as it takes 10 min for cobalt determination.

Experimental

Electronic spectra were recorded on a Carl-Zeiss 330 Specol spectrophotometer using 1 cm matched pair of cells and ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 221 spectrophotometer. An Elico pH meter was used for the measurement of pH.

The reagent (8-MeO-2-chloro-QAT) was prepared

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL PARAMETERS FOR DETERMINATION OF Co^{II} AND Cu^{II}

Parameter	Co ^{II}	Cu ^{II}
λ_{max} (nm)	400	410
ϵ_{max} ($\times 10^{-3}$ dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	57844	26768
Stability of colour (h)	30	24
pH	6	5
Beer's law range (ppm)	4	3
Sandell's sensitivity (g)	0.020	0.010
Optimum range (ppm)	1.8-3.8	1.5-3.8
Dissociation constant	1.442×10^{-7}	8.082×10^{-5}
Metal ligand ratio	1 : 1	1 : 1

In aqueous media the complexes are precipitated. They are soluble in 20% (v/v) DMF-water medium. The reaction is quite rapid and requires no heating

by the standard method² by refluxing equimolar quantities of 8-methoxy-2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde and thiosemicarbazide in minimum amount of ethanol for 1 h, m.p. 185–186° (Analysis : C, 48.92; H, 3.8; N, 19.07%); ν_{\max} 1 270–1 190 (C=S), 1 580–1 600 (C=C), 2 220–3 100 cm^{-1} (NH); λ_{\max} 360 nm (ϵ_{\max} $0.7 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$).

Stock solutions (1 mg ml^{-1}) of Co^{II} and Cu^{II} were prepared from cobalt sulphate heptahydrate and copper sulphate respectively, and standardised³. Buffer solution for Cu^{II} was prepared from 0.2 N acetic acid and 0.2 N sodium acetate (pH 5) and that

for Co^{II} from 0.2 N acetic acid and 0.2 N sodium acetate (pH 6).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Head of Chemistry Department, Shivaji University, for facilities.

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